

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THE FIBRE BUNDLE PERMEABILITY AS A FUNCTION OF SATURATION

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SUMMARY: This paper deals with the experimental determination of the permeability of a fibre bundle in dependence of the saturation $K(\theta)$. The knowledge of $K(\theta)$ is necessary to accurately predict voids creation during Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) processes. To predict the voids the impregnation process is simulated on meso scale level. The meso-flow is the flow through and around fibre bundles. Bundles permeability is strongly influenced by the saturation. It increases with the impregnation degree of the bundle.

To measure $K(\theta)$, a test liquid is pumped with a constant flow rate through the fibre bundles. The degree of saturation is kept constant. Flow rate and pressure gradient are measured. The measurement shows some problems related to the adjustment control of the degree of saturation. The problems are discussed and an improved set-up is proposed.

KEYWORDS: permeability, saturation, fibre bundle, meso scale

INTRODUCTION

The Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) process is a well understood process on macroscopic scale. Macroscopic flow and mould filling can be simulated in a reliable manner. Nevertheless, prediction of the voids creation is still difficult. The detrimental influence of the voids on the mechanical properties is well known [1, 2] as well as the principal reasons for voids creation.

Fig. 1: Fingering at the flow-front

If the flow front is not evenly shaped, air is entrapped (figure 1). Fingering effects as shown in Figure 1 are a consequence of different inter- and intra-flow velocities resulting from capillary effects or due to varying permeabilities in the fibre bed. [3]

The long-term aim of this project is to investigate the meso flow to better describe and predict the voids creation during the impregnation in the LCM process. In this contribution the measurement of partially saturated glass fibre bundles is investigated experimentally. The measured values are needed as input for the simulation of the impregnation process of a fabric on meso scale.

THEORETICAL ASPECTS

In the LCM process, a fibre preform is impregnated with resin. The preform is a dual-scale porous medium: it consists of fibre bundles which are composed of thousands of fibres. The gaps between the bundles are in the order of 0.1 mm. The interstitial spaces between the singles fibres are in the order of micrometers. The flow in the fibre bundles is described by Darcy's law whereas the flow in the fibre free regions can be modelled using Navier-Stokes. At the interface between the two regions Brinkman's equation can be used. In the next paragraphs the flow through partially saturated porous media is described and an explanation is given why the presence of air is a dominant factor for transport processes in porous media.

Flow through porous media

Fibre bundles are treated as a porous medium. Their mathematical description is taken from earth physics. Flow of a liquid through a saturated porous media is commonly described using Darcy's law:

$$q = -\frac{K}{\eta} \nabla p \quad (1)$$

q is the Darcy-velocity, the flow of the resin penetrating the fibres, K the permeability of the preform, η the viscosity of the resin and ∇p the pressure gradient [4].

The permeability describes the conductivity of a porous medium. There are several equations which describe the permeability such as the well known Cozeny-Carman equation [5]:

$$K = \frac{r^2}{4k} \frac{\phi^3}{(1-\phi)^2} \quad (2)$$

where r is the average radius of the fibres, k the empirical Kozeny constant and ϕ the porosity. In (3), the permeability increases with increasing porosity.

Flow through partially saturated porous media is a multiphase flow, consisting of resin and air.

Accordingly Darcy's law must be replaced by the Buckingham-Darcy equation:

$$q(\theta) = -\frac{K(\theta)}{\eta} \nabla p \quad (3)$$

The permeability is not a constant anymore, but a function of the degree of saturation θ , leading to a non-linear velocity and pressure gradient. [6,7]

Permeability can be expressed as a function of the degree of saturation:

$$K(\theta) = k_{rel}(\theta) * K_{sat} \quad (4)$$

The relative permeability $k_{rel}(\theta)$ of the liquid varies between 0 and 1.

There are three factors influencing the conductivity of the fibre bed:

- (1) The area of liquid-filled pore space available to flow depends on the saturation degree. Air acts in the same way on the liquid flow as if the air was a solid. De Parseval has illustrated this influence for a fabric in figure 2. The effective flow cross section increases with the saturation. In region 1, liquid flows around the fibre tows. The impregnation of the tows begins in region 2. The preform is completely impregnated in region 3. The liquid flows through the whole flow cross section of the preform. This idea can be applied on single fibre bundles, too.

Fig. 2: Dependence of the permeability on the fabric saturation [8]

- (2) At low saturation, the big channels are filled with air, and resin flows through the small and more tortuous flow paths due to capillary forces. The tortuosity of the paths elongates the flow length and decreases the applied pressure gradient: the driving force diminishes.
- (3) The flow in the channels can be described with the law of Hagen-Poiseuille:

$$v(r') = \frac{r^2}{4\eta} \frac{\nabla p}{\nabla x} \left[1 - \left[\frac{r'}{r} \right]^2 \right] \quad (5)$$

r' is the distance to the centre of the capillary, r the radius of the capillary, η the viscosity of the liquid and ∇p the pressure difference over the length ∇x . At the centre of the capillary $v(r'=0)$ is maximal and vanishes at the wall, the interface liquid-solid, $v(r'=r)$. In small capillaries the velocity is slower than in bigger ones. There are two reasons:

1. The maximal velocity $v(r'=0)$ in the centre of the capillary decreases with decreasing radius r of the capillary.
2. In narrow capillaries the ratio flow area to interface, where the velocity is zero, is smaller than in wider capillaries. This can be seen in the following equation:

$$\frac{A}{U \cdot h} = \frac{2\pi r^2}{2\pi r} = \frac{r}{h} \propto r \quad (6)$$

The quotient flow area A over perimeter U and height h is proportional to the radius r .

The average flow velocity is smaller at low saturation. [6,9]

Thus, the liquid conductivity increases with increasing saturation.

Capillary effects

Capillary effects appear in the unsaturated flow in the LCM process. In the saturated state they vanish. Capillary pressure P_C is described by the following equation:

$$P_C = -\frac{\sigma_{lv} 2 \cos \alpha}{r} \quad (7)$$

σ_{lv} is the surface tension of the liquid, α the contact angle and r the radius of the capillary. P_C depends on the degree of saturation. Its maximum is in the unsaturated state. It decreases with increasing saturation. [10]

The capillary pressure influences Darcy's Flow. It increases the driving force. The acting pressure on the resin is the applied injection pressure P_{in} plus the amount of the capillary pressure: $p = P_{in} - P_C$. Darcy's flow changes to:

$$q = -\frac{K}{\eta} \nabla (P_{in} - P_{out}) \quad (8)$$

If the resin and air are treated as one pseudo mono fluid, the influence of the capillary pressure on the Darcy flow is integrated in the relative permeability k_{rel} . In k_{rel} all effects of the changing saturation, the altering permeability and capillary pressure, are included:

$$q = -\frac{k(\theta)_{rel} * K_{sat}}{\mu} \nabla p \quad (9)$$

The relative permeability $k(\theta)_{rel}$ varies between the ratio of permeability $R_s = \frac{K_{unsat}}{K_{sat}}$ and 1.

K_{sat} is the permeability of the saturated preform, K_{unsat} the one of the unsaturated preform.[11] This equation is very useful to measure the necessary inputs to simulate the unsaturated flow. In only one measurement, the unsaturated permeability and the influence of capillary effects can be determined.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The principle of the measurement is to keep a constant degree of saturation of the partially saturated fibre bundles while a liquid is injected through the fibres.

To determine the permeability as a function of saturation we developed and built an experimental set-up based on those typically used in soil physics (Figures 3). The device consists of a plexiglas cylinder holding the fibres. Its diameter d is 54mm and its height h is 50mm. It is closed by two circular steel plates. In the upper plate is the inflow and in the bottom one the outlet.

Fig. 3: Experimental set-up

A test liquid is injected with a constant flow rate through the fibre bundles, whereas the degree of saturation should be kept constant. A punched plate is placed above the fibres to enable a distribution of the liquid over the whole flow area. Additionally, air is added to disable complete saturation of the fibres.

Pressure gradient and flow rate are measured for a specific degree of saturation. Knowing the viscosity of the liquid, the permeability can then be calculated using the Buckingham–Darcy equation. The saturation of the fibres is controlled via the mass. At the beginning of each measurement the balance is tare to zero. The measured mass corresponds to the impregnating liquid. The air-flow is determined with a mass flow sensor.

In the actual set-up, permeability is measured longitudinal to the fibre bundles. The orientation of the fibres is assumed to be parallel. Glass fibres, EC9 68 Z28 T8G H8 from SAINT-GOBAIN VETROTEX, have a fibre diameter of 9 μm . The test liquid is Glycerin with a viscosity of 0.05 Pas.

RESULTS

The measured pressure gradients are in a range of 0.1 bar to 1 bar. The flow rates of the liquid vary between $2\text{E-}14$ l/min and $1\text{E-}13$ l/min. The flow rates of air are in the order of 50 l/min at an injection pressure of 1 bar.

There are several problems in the realisation of the measurement:

1. It is very difficult to keep the mass constant over a long time. Figure 4 shows the measured values at the beginning of a measurement. This means, at the beginning, the fibres are dry, the mass is zero. During the measurement their saturation increases in accordance to the mass. The saturation of the fibre bundles is 25 % at a mass of 12g. The upper horizontal line (OUT (V)) is the reference value of the voltage of the pump. The IN (V) values are the working voltage of the pump. The flow rate is $3.7\text{E-}06$ m/s (corresponds to $8.6\text{E-}09$ m³/s) at a working voltage of 0.9 V. The little step in the mass at 6g results supposedly from a vibration in the laboratory. At the end of this measurement, the voltage of the pump is reduced. As a result the mass and according to it the saturation maintains constant.

Fig. 4: Example of measured values

2. A homogenous distribution of the liquid and air between the fibres is hardly to adjust. At low degrees of saturation, the resin is concentrated in one part of the fibres and the other fibres are dry (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Liquid distribution

3. A controlled method of simultaneous injection of air and liquid to distribute them homogeneously failed. The volume of air and liquid should be controlled to inject the same volume of both at the same time. The measured air volume passing through the fibres is over hundred times the volume of the injected liquid volume. Air has a higher mobility than the used liquid. This huge difference in the mobilities prevents a successful injection control, for example 50% air and 50% liquid.
4. The liquid prefers to flow through big channels between the fibres. The channels dilate with increasing pressure (Fig. 6). Wider channels lead to a higher conductivity. Hence, the permeability is pressure dependent.

Fig. 6: Channel between fibres

Figure 7 shows some results of the longitudinal permeability of two samples having a fibre volume content of 58%. The scaling of the ordinate is logarithmic. The results are much dispersed. The values of sample 2 are except the first one below the ones of sample 1. One reason for this deviation is the different wide channels. Probably, sample 1 has wider channels than sample 2 resulting in a higher permeability.

The trend of the values of both samples shows an increase of the permeability with increasing saturation corresponding to the expectations, although the distribution of the two media was

not homogenous. This problem is explainable considering which permeability is measured: The measured permeability of all fibres is composed of the permeability of the flow through the impregnated part and the dry part. The impregnated regions and the dry ones act like a parallel connexion. As the liquid flow through the dry part is zero, its permeability is zero. The measured permeability is the permeability of the impregnated part. The flow area of this impregnated part increases with increasing saturation, so the entire permeability, too. This increase is not linear due to the additional air pressure.

Fig. 7: Permeability as function of the degree of saturation for two samples

CONCLUSIONS

Results show that it is very difficult to measure the permeability in dependence of the saturation. The most serious problem is the inhomogeneous distribution of the liquid. To improve the measurement, the method must be changed. Instead of trying to keep the degree of saturation constant, pressure gradients should be measured directly in the partially saturated zone during the impregnation. Several pressure sensors have to be positioned directly between the fibres. Some very small pressure sensors are needed for this setup disabling a disturbance of the flow. The different permeabilities of the differently impregnated zones should have varied pressure gradients. Figure 8 illustrates the theoretical pressure curve. In zone 1, the less saturated zone directly behind the flow front, the permeability is low and the pressure gradient high. Zone 2 is more saturated resulting in a lower pressure gradient. Zone 3 and 4 are again more saturated having a lesser pressure gradient. Zone 5 is fully saturated with the highest permeability and the lowest pressure gradient. The slope of the pressure gradient depends on the saturation and has to be used to calculate the permeability in dependence of the saturation.

Fig. 8: Flow length pressure diagram

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